

Behaviour of Nickel Amalgams in Phosphoric Acid Solutions

R. ABOU SHAHBA*, N. S. HASSAN, A. S. AHMED and S. M. ROSHDY

Al-Azhar University, Faculty of Science (for Girls), Chemistry Department, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 26 September 1988, revised 8 February 1990, accepted 7 May 1990

Nickel amalgams of varying concentrations were anodically oxidised galvanostatically in phosphoric acid solutions at 25°. For nickel amalgams two different oxidation patterns were distinguished—the first in concentrated (1.0 and 3.0 N H₃PO₄) and the second in dilute (0.1 N H₃PO₄) acid solutions.

The relation between the polarising current (*i*) and the time of passivation (τ) was found to follow the relation, $\log \tau = A - n \log i$, where *i* and *n* are constants. The diffusion of nickel within the amalgam to the amalgam/electrolyte interface was mainly rate-determining in the process of passivation. The effect of temperature on the time of passivation of nickel amalgams in phosphoric acid solution was also investigated.

THE literature is rich regarding the oxidation and passivation of metallic alloys. Certain rules are put to explain and predict the beneficial or detrimental effects resulting from incorporating traces of one metal in the bulk of the other. Little work has been directed, however, to the study of alloys in which mercury forms the main constituent. Moreover, nickel and its alloys possess excellent corrosion resistance in a wide variety of environments. This naturally raises considerable interest in investigating the cause of passivity of nickel. Several techniques have been employed to characterise the nature and thickness of the surface film. However, conflicting views exist regarding the nature and mechanism of formation of the passive film.

Therefore, the main objective of the present study was to investigate the composition of the film formed on a nickel amalgam electrode and throw more light on the mechanism leading to the electrode passivation.

Experimental

The electrical cell and experimental details were similar to those given previously¹. The mercury electrode was in the form of a small cup (1.67 cm i.d.) provided with a sealed platinum wire. The cathode was in the form of an auxillary electrode with a sealed platinum contact. In order to avoid the contamination of the tested solution with the cathodic products, the cathode was isolated from the electrolytic solution. It was achieved by auxillary electrode in a special compartment fitted with a sintered-glass disc of medium porosity. The potential of the working electrode was measured against a saturated calomel electrode. All potentials are referred to the reversible hydrogen electrode scale.

The amalgam of the electrodes were prepared electrolytically *in situ* from the acid plating baths having the following composition: NiSO₄·7H₂O,

90 g; NiCl₂·6H₂O, 30 g; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 16 g; H₃PO₄, 30 ml and NH₄Cl, 4.5 g cm⁻³.

A known amounts of solution was introduced into the electrode cup containing double-distilled mercury (1.5 ml) and electrolysis was carried out with a fixed current of 50 mA/electrode for nickel with mercury acting as the cathode. The electrode area was 2.30 cm². The mercury and electrolyte were continuously stirred. Complete plating of the metal was marked by the brisk evolution of hydrogen gas from the surface of the electrode. Electrolysis was continued for a further 30 min period. The amalgam was washed several times with double-distilled water and then dried with narrow strips of filter paper. Complete deposition of nickel was ascertained by atomic absorption analysis.

Amalgams varying in concentration between 0.6448×10^{-2} to 3.8557×10^{-2} (wt%) nickel were prepared (Table 1). 3.0, 1.0 and 0.1 N solutions of orthophosphoric acid was used as testing media.

TABLE 1—AMALGAM ELECTRODE COMPOSITION

Electrode no.	Ni $\times 10^{-2}$ wt%	Mole fraction $\times 10^{-3}$
I	0 644 8	2 261 5
II	2 573 8	8 696 5
III	3 855 7	12 988 0

Results and Discussion

Anodic and cathodic polarisation curves for nickel amalgams with increasing metal content were traced in 0.1, 1.0 and 3.0 N H₃PO₄ solutions at 25°. For each amalgam solution composition, a number of constant polarising currents was applied to gain insight into the mechanism of passivation. The results showed two different oxidation patterns. The first describes the behaviour of the nickel amalgams in concentrated acid solutions (1.0 and 3.0 N H₃PO₄)

Fig. 1. Anodic, cathodic and decay polarisation of electrode-III of Ni-amalgam in 3 N H₃PO₄ with c.d. values: (○) 600, (×) 522, (△) 435, (●) 348 and (□) 261 μA cm⁻².

and the second in dilute acid solutions (0.1 N H₃PO₄).

Behaviour of nickel amalgams in concentrated acid solutions: Under a wide range of constant polarising current densities and solution concentration (1 and 3N H₃PO₄), nickel amalgams (electrodes I, II and III) yield polarisation curves which exhibit practically the same features.

Fig. 1 represents the potential-time curves of nickel amalgam electrode (electrode-III) in 3.0 N H₃PO₄ solution. The curves having the same features were also obtained using electrode-I (1.0 N H₃PO₄). It can be seen that the primary anodic process in the polarisation curves represents the charging of the anodic double layer, then the Ni of the amalgam dissolves as Ni²⁺ along region (i) (showing no inflection) according to the equation,

As a fair approximation the activity of nickel in mercury could be set equal to its mole fraction χ_{Ni} , shown in Table 1.

Substituting these values in the Nernst equation,

$$E = E^0 + 0.059 \text{ pH} - 0.029 \log \chi_{\text{Ni}} \quad (2)$$

gave for the three amalgams in 0.1, 1 and 3 N H₃PO₄, values of *E* varying from -0.093 to -0.133 V. Formation of Ni²⁺ along this region (i) in the polarisation curves, corresponds to the first period of activity of nickel amalgams which is then oxidised to NiO (region ii) showing no inflection also.

Formation of NiO along region (ii) in galvanostatic studies was also reported by previous authors² who reported that small constant c.d. causes the potential of nickel electrode to increase suddenly to a value that corresponds to the reversible NiO/Ni

potential. Similar observations were also made by Besson³ on the anodic oxidation of nickel electrode in 6 N KOH solution by Rollet's method and reported the transformation equilibria together with the respective oxidation reduction potentials (in V) determined at the points of inflection of the anodic Potential-time curves,

The formation of NiO along region (ii) was followed by five clear arrests. Along arrests I and II, mercurous and mercuric phosphate are formed and surface of the amalgam electrode was covered with a white deposit.

That mercurous and mercuric phosphate are formed during arrests I and II in the polarisation curves is corroborated by a consideration of Fig. 2 in which pure mercury is oxidised in 1N H₃PO₄ acid under identical experimental conditions of c.d., solution concentration and temperature.

Further confirmation for the formation of mercurous and mercuric phosphate along arrests I and II respectively, was obtained from the open-circuit potential that arises from these salts on the surface of a clean double-distilled mercury pool where values of 625 and 675 mV were obtained for mercurous and mercuric phosphate respectively.

Due to the solubility of mercurous and mercuric phosphates in acids, an elongation of the step showing formation of mercuric phosphate occurs (Fig. 1); and oscillations occur in the potential-time curve (specially in dilute solutions, Fig. 3) due to the continuous formation and dissolution of the salt layer.

Fig 2 Anodic, cathodic and decay polarisation of Hg in 1 N H₃PO₄ at c d 261 μA cm⁻²

Fig 3 Anodic, cathodic and decay polarisation of electrode-II of Ni-amalgam in 0.1 N H₃PO₄ with c d values : (C) 435, (x) 348, (Δ) 304 and (●) 260 μA cm⁻²

Owing to the liquid nature of the electrode, the primary passivating film contained fissures and cracks which allowed the amalgam to come in contact with the solution and the NiO formed at the first stage of passivity (region ii) would be oxidised to higher oxides along steps III and IV according to the reaction,

Ni₂O₃ which is formed along step IV is further oxidised to NiO₂ along arrest V, according to the reaction⁴,

before finally the potential rises to the oxygen evolution values.

These results are in agreement with those obtained by previous authors on solid nickel electrodes in sodium phosphate solution⁵. They suggested that the passive film on nickel electrode has a duplex structure consisting of NiO and Ni₃O₄. At high potential NiO₂ was produced on top of the initial film.

Cathodic polarisation curves were traced by reversing the polarising currents when the potential was at oxygen evolution values (curve C, Fig. 1) so as to make the working electrode the cathode.

Three arrests appeared in the cathodic polarisation curve. The first two correspond to the reduction of mercuric and mercurous phosphate according to

the reactions,

Then reduction of NiO_2 to NiO took place along the third arrest before the final potential drops to hydrogen evolution values.

Anodic decay curves obtained upon interrupting the polarising current when the electrode was at oxygen evolution values (curve D, Fig. 1), indicated that potential dropped directly to values corresponding to the system $\text{Hg}_3\text{PO}_4/\text{Hg}_2\text{HPO}_4$ where the potential remains constant thereafter.

Behaviour of nickel amalgams in dilute phosphoric acid solutions: Quite interesting is the oxidation characteristics of nickel amalgams in dilute solutions. In Fig. 3 shows the anodic polarisation curves for electrode-II in 0.1 N H_3PO_4 acid. It can be seen that the charging of the anodic double layer and dissolution of Ni as Ni^{2+} followed by its oxidation to NiO (as mentioned earlier) in concentrated phosphoric acid solutions (1 and 3 N) was then followed by a region of oscillations which may probably be due to the fact that the formed mercurous and mercuric phosphate are soluble in acid phosphate solutions⁶. The layers in these dilute solutions once formed readily dissolves and fluctuations occur in the anodic polarisation curves due to the formation and breakdown of these salts at the first stage of passivity. After some time the NiO formed at the early stages of passivity is oxidised to Ni_3O_4 along step I in the polarisation curve (Fig. 3) which is then successively oxidised to Ni_2O_3 and NiO_2 along steps III and IV as given before in case of concentrated phosphoric acid solutions.

Relation between polarising current (i) and time of passivation (τ): In order to gain further insight on the nature of the process that eventually leads to the electrode passivation (film formation), the plots between the polarising current i (μA) and time

of passivation τ (min) were considered. Plots of these two variables for electrode-III in 0.1, 1.0 and 3N H_3PO_4 solutions gave almost parallel straight lines with slope values of -2 in excellent agreement with $n=2$, predicted by Muller's empirical formula and Sand's equation for electrolysis with constant current (chronopotentiometry)⁷. Similar observations were also found for electrodes I and II in phosphoric acid solutions.

The passivation of the different nickel amalgams in the examined solutions are satisfactorily represented by the relation,

$$\log \tau = A - n \log i \quad (8)$$

where A and n are constants.

Table 2 gives the values of the constant A while the value of n in all cases was 2.

Electrode no	Solution of H_3PO_4		
	3 N	1 N	0.1 N
I	7.49	7.51	6.40
II	7.80	7.65	6.47
III	7.89	7.69	7.18

From the results of the present investigation the passivation of nickel amalgams in H_3PO_4 solutions appears to be largely governed by the rate of diffusion of nickel atoms to the electrode/electrolyte interface.

Effect of temperature on time of passivations of nickel amalgams in phosphoric acid solution: The results of the anodic polarisation of electrode-II in 1 N H_3PO_4 solution at different temperatures and at a c.d. of $261 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ are shown in Fig. 4. As is seen that the time of passivation increases with rise of temperature. Since the potential-time curves are analogous in shape at higher and lower temperatures, save for the increased time of passivation at higher

Fig 4 Effect of temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) in electrode-II in 1.0 N H_3PO_4 at c.d. $261 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. (O) 45° , (\times) 35° , (Δ) 30° , (\bullet) 20° and (\square) 10° .

temperatures, the effect of temperature may be accounted for as due to the increased solubilities of the layers initially present or anodically formed on the electrode surface, thereby increasing the time needed for the passivation of the electrodes.

References

- 1 H M SAMMOUR, L A KAMEL and S M ROUSHDI, *Corrosion Sci* , 1973, **13**, 939
- 2 T S DE GROMOBOY and L L. SHREIR, *Electrochim. Acta* , 1966, **11**, 895
- 3 J BESSON, *Chem Abstr* , 1964, **40**, 60057
- 4 M POURBAIX, "Atlas of Electrochemical Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions", Pergamon, New York, 1966.
- 5 M OKUYAMA and S HARUYAMA, *Corrosion Sci* , 1974, **41**, 1
- 6 C Y CHAO, Z S SMIALOWSKA and D D MACDONALD, *J Electroanal Chem* , 1982, **131**, 289.
7. H J S SAND, *Phil. Mag.*, 1901, **1**